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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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Description (short)
The report will describe the set-up of the pilot focus groups on ENLIGHT flagship challenges and the action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications in their specific domain.

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INTRODUCTION

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ENLIGHT is a European University Alliance to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher Education Transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries.

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and more specifically within the Science With and For Society (SWAFS) Work Programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT Alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The main objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) of ENLIGHT RISE is to **create synergies through R&I capacity building**. Complementing the mapping of expertise in the ENLIGHT Think Tank (Erasmus+), WP2 analyses the alliance members' scientific and technological profiles and tries to exploit the synergies leading to maximize ENLIGHT Alliance's competitive advantage (task 2.1). WP2 Research & Innovation Observatory will help identifying ENLIGHT R&I capacities (task 2.2) and WP2 Pilot Focus Groups will lead the strategic orientation for building competitive R&I collaborations among them (task 2.3). At the same time, WP2 Pilot Focus Groups will help Work Package 1 ("Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda") prioritize R&I support activities.

In order to drive competitive joint Research & Innovation initiatives on flagship challenges¹ within the alliance, the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 is working to establish some pilot focus groups on ENLIGHT flagship challenges. These groups will coordinate the emergence and/or expansion of collaborative R&I actions within ENLIGHT and establish an action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications in their specific domain, in close interaction with the R&I Support Group (R&I SG)² (WP1 Establish a sustainable business model towards a collaborative R&I agenda).

This document represents D11 (D2.3) and describes the setting up of the Pilot Focus Groups in each of the ENLIGHT flagship domains, their aims, composition, expected tasks and action plan. The future deliverable D12 (D2.4), to be published in month 24 (August 2023) will update the action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications in their specific flagship domain, based on new work programmes and funding opportunities that may arise, as well as based on the feedback of the first joint proposals that may have been submitted.

¹ Flagship areas: Health and Well-Being; Digital revolution; Climate action; Energy transition & Circular Economy; Equity. For more information, please consult this page: <https://enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/flagship-domains> :

² The R&I SG is a working group of research support officers from all nine universities which aims at identifying synergies that can be achieved in different sources of EC funding ; facilitating/incentivizing research collaborations.

1. THE ENLIGHT RISE FOCUS GROUPS

Guidelines for the ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups have been set up in order to give the main information on the aim, themes, composition, expected tasks and outcomes of the Focus Groups.

AIM OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

The overall objective of these Focus Groups is to **coordinate the emergence and expansion of mission-oriented R&I projects, building on the ENLIGHT alliance R&I capacities and leading to successful grant applications around the flagship challenges.**

This main goal can be decoupled in some specific action lines that will guide the Focus Groups activity:

- ✓ Community building: getting to know each other, the different expertise available in relation to the flagship domain at each institution, and the interest for establishing collaborations;
- ✓ Identification of the right expertise at each university and facilitate the connection between them;
- ✓ Establishment of an action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications; and
- ✓ Activation of pilot R&I projects on flagship domains.

THEMATIC AREAS

The ENLIGHT alliance focuses its action around five big challenges that are key determinants of societal well-being and sustainability (ENLIGHT flagships):

- **Health and Well-being:**
Urban Health with a special focus on (i) the impact of aging populations, especially on brain and mental health, (ii) the impact of environmental exposures and inequalities in healthcare access, and (iii) opportunities for future cities through precision medicine and digital public health.
- **Digital Revolution and Impact of digitization:**
AI for Good in our cities and communities, with a special focus on digital simulation to support decision-making, AI and health, AI and sustainable society.
- **Climate change:**
Climate change and urban development with a special focus on: (i) impact of climate change on land use, socio-ecosystems, relation between cities and surrounding rural areas, (ii) mitigation through improved environmental impact assessment, intersectoral initiatives for climate neutrality.
- **Energy and Circular Economy:**
Energy conversion and transition with a special focus on multidisciplinary approaches to (i) energy transition, (ii) circularity, and (iii) raw material value chain.
- **Equity:**
Addressing polarization in our cities and communities, with a special focus on (i) urban development and marginalization, (ii) access and equity in future cities for long-term sustainability, (iii) sustainable heritage and polarization.

The ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups will correspond to this thematic division meaning there will be five Focus Groups, one for each of the ENLIGHT Flagships.

COMPOSITION

1. Procedure for the composition of the Focus Groups

The Focus Groups' members are nominated by the universities according to their profile and qualifications, which should be relevant to the competences of the flagship domain and aligned with the following profile description.

The composition may evolve depending on the need for more specific expertise, skills and/or interest for collaboration.

2. The focus group member profile

The Focus Groups are ideally composed by a variety of profiles that will enrich the co-creation process, including (among others) the following ones:

Scientific profiles: Researchers at different stages of career having expertise in the thematic areas of the five ENLIGHT flagship areas, more specifically:

- ✓ Senior researchers specialized in a theme linked to the focus group specific flagship domain (from R3 (Established Researcher) to R4 (Leading Researcher), as defined by Euraxess research profile descriptors³); and
- ✓ Junior researchers with any background that could contribute to any of the flagship areas (R2 (Recognised Researcher, i.e. PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)).

Research and Support staff profiles:

- ✓ One to two ENLIGHT universities' research support officers (RSOs) per focus group. These RSOs may be also part of the ENLIGHT R&I Support Group.

3. Additional recommendations to be considered for the composition of the focus groups

- ✓ Gender balance should be encouraged;
- ✓ One to two researcher representatives per university per group (ideally one junior and one senior researcher according to the definition set above in section 2);
- ✓ In the light of the synergies and complementarities between the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ and ENLIGHT RISE initiatives, the participation of researchers already members of ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Core Groups is welcome;
- ✓ Each Focus Group should be research and innovation-based.

EXPECTED TASKS

³ <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/europe/career-development/training-researchers/research-profiles-descriptors>

Members of the focus groups are expected to carry out the following (non-exhaustive) list of tasks:

- ✓ **Participation in, and when decided so, coordination of a Focus Group;**
- ✓ **Identify and encourage research and innovation collaborations within the ENLIGHT alliance context:**
 - Share and exchange expertise in R&I in the flagship domains;
 - Initiate R&I initiatives in the flagship field at the local university level;
 - Identify new research collaborations.
- ✓ **Undertake R&I project collaborations:**
 - Share and exchange R&I opportunities;
 - Identify relevant calls for proposals;
 - Develop innovative collaborative research projects, involving a minimum of 3 ENLIGHT universities;
 - Develop bottom-up collaborations.
- ✓ **Define and update a road map for each group;**
- ✓ **Foster synergies and complementarities with ENLIGHT education and training activities;**
- ✓ **Liaise with ENLIGHT Erasmus+ think tank (see section below "Action plan/ links with Erasmus+ Core Groups) in terms of new research opportunities, collaborations and priorities for local partners.**

RECOMMENDED OPERATIVE FRAMEWORK

- ✓ During the first months, it is expected that the members of each group will meet once a month to get to know each other, identify relevant initiatives for collaboration and be able to propose a road map for the group.
- ✓ Each focus group will be led by a leading trio with rotating coordination. The leading trio will be nominated during the first meetings of the group.
- ✓ The focus group will count with managerial and administrative support by the ENLIGHT RISE WP2 team.

OUTPUTS

During the first round of the Focus Groups there are three main expected outputs:

- **Draft road map.** The focus group members will jointly initiate and develop a road map for their group;
- **Short list of complementary research themes.** The focus groups will identify common research topics/ priorities and sub-topics/ priorities to drive joint collaborations/ proposals;
- **External funding opportunities.** The focus groups will identify and should respond to at least one research and innovation call for proposals.

2. ACTION PLAN

As detailed above, each focus group will propose its road map to prioritize and develop its own actions. Each group will have to describe its action plan, the ambition and the planned activities. A template will be proposed to them containing the following items:

- **Action description:**
 - o summary, expected impact and results, complementarity/expertise of partners;
 - o Innovative and strategic aspects of the action;
 - o Long-term goals and sustainability of the cooperation;
 - o European/International call identified (if any) & deadline foreseen.
- **Reverse Schedule;**
- **Expected and Desired Impact on ENLIGHT Flagships/Europe/Society.**

Links with Erasmus+ CORE GROUPS and THINK TANK

In order to reinforce synergies and complementarities between the education and the research and innovation components of the ENLIGHT alliance, a foreseen development and sustainability element for the focus groups is to use the existing ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Think Tank structure. The ENLIGHT Erasmus+ Think Tank is a space for innovation and interconnecting know-how in the flagship domains. It is an inter-university sharing platform regrouping the Erasmus+ core groups (education component of the Alliance) across the nine universities. It enables the members to share the data and milestones of their flagship domain and to identify transversal topics within the flagship areas.

The Think Tank would be then seen as an umbrella for both the education and research and innovation components of the ENLIGHT alliance, enabling the exchange of information, synergies and complementarities with the two independent subgroups (the Core Groups and the Focus Groups) per thematic area.

CONCLUSION and NEXT STEPS

This document, which is an active document, described the setting up of the ENLIGHT RISE Focus Groups, their aims, composition, expected tasks and action plan. It will be complemented by the future deliverable D12 (D2.4) to be published in month 24 (August 2023) which will update the action plan for prioritizing pilot projects and funding applications in the Focus Groups specific domains, based on new work programmes and funding opportunities that may arise as well as based on the feedback of first joint proposals that may have been submitted.